

OApoly: The game about scientific publishing

SHORT OVERVIEW

The game OApoly simulates the journey of researchers who publish scientific findings and enhance their visibility. The goal of the game is to establish oneself in the scientific community by working sustainably and following open access policies as closely as possible, while earning reputation points.

The game also informs about the diverse tasks that academic libraries undertake today in an entertaining way, such as providing publication guidance, managing research data, or establishing fair open access structures. At the same time, it demonstrates how public funds are utilized within the academic system and the societal value of open and free access to knowledge. OApoly makes it clear: open science strengthens transparency, participation, and democracy.

BACKGROUND AND CONCEPT

From concept to game

The original idea for OApoly emerged during preparations for an open house at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). Explaining the different models of open access publishing is always a challenge for libraries, not only when communicating with non-academics, but also with researchers at their institution or students who are just taking their first steps in their academic careers.

The development of the game OApoly was the result of our search for a game concept that symbolizes the flow of money in publishing and, if possible, introduces various terms related to the publishing industry. The basic idea was based on well-known board games but was specifically adapted to our requirements. After a few brainstorming sessions and test games with pen and paper, the first version of our current OApoly game was created in a short period of 6 months.

Objective from the librarian's perspective

The main goal is to introduce various groups of individuals to the topic of scientific publishing while showcasing the services offered by the KIT Library. The game should be as accessible as possible to engage with non-academic visitors as well. At the same time, the level of difficulty can be adapted depending on the specific audience.

In the case of external visitors, the game aims to open the topic of scientific publishing in a lighthearted way and introduce them to the themes. It is not expected that all participants are familiar with all terms in detail by the end of the game. Nevertheless, the scope can be adjusted for an academic audience by enhancing the duration and expanding the depth of explanations when suitable.

Therefore, OApoly provides various possible use cases in information literacy and teaching library purposes. The game is suitable for showcasing at conferences or can be used as an internal onboarding event. The possibilities for its use are diverse.

In addition, the game materials and accompanying resources offer a versatile way to include library-related information for respective libraries, e.g., by adding QR codes on the game cards with links to the respective library's landing page or open access services. The certificate taken home by players works as a small memento and provides space for a QR code and more information on the topic and services.

WHY THE NAME OApoly?

The name OApoly is derived from the term “monopoly”, or more specifically, “oligopoly”. For a long time, scientific publishing has no longer been a system supported only by science itself but largely commercialized. In recent decades, this resulted in the formation of oligopoly-style of systems led by a few publishers, which enhanced their own prestige and economic standing. Quality and impact are no longer the only standards. Even as the number of open-access systems grows and Diamond Open Access publishers emerge, the market remains concentrated among a few large publishers. The term OApoly is a reference on this system and the game further illustrates ways besides the established ones by showcasing the library services.

Game Material

- Game spaces/fields (for building the gaming area)
- Action Cards
- Coins
- Reputation Points
- Certificates
- Dice
- Game Manual in a poster form

The spaces, action cards, certificates, reputation points, and the poster are available as printable material.

Game Setup

The playing fields can be arranged in a square, leaving the center empty. We suggest the following setup, thematically ordered:

1. Start field
2. Team Bibliometrics+Reporting
3. Closed Access
4. Action Card
5. Office Good Scientific Practice
6. Repository (KIT version: KITopen)
7. Green Open Access
8. Action Card
9. Copyright Trap
10. Publicationfund (KIT version: KIT Publication Fund)
11. Gold Open Access
12. Action Card
13. Research Data Management (KIT version: RDM@KIT)
14. Universtity Publishing (KIT version: KIT Scientific Publishing)
15. Diamond Open Access
16. Action Card

GAMEPLAY AND GOAL

As an emerging researcher, the player tries to earn a reputation by achieving impact and visibility.

At the start each player has 0 reputation points and 5 Coins, which symbolize project funding.

Each player rolls the dice in turn and moves over the play area according to the number rolled.

- If the player lands on a library or open access space, they follow the corresponding action.
- If the player lands on an action card space, they draw an action card and follow the instruction. Action cards are either helpful or a challenge.

The game ends when one player has collected 5 reputation points.

This player has earned great scientific impact and visibility and is the winner of the game!

THE PLAYING FIELDS

Each playing space represents either a type of open access publication or one of the various services of a library concerning scientific publications. In addition, there are neutral spaces, such as "Start" and "Action Field." The following explanations indicate the number of points one can earn at each field. The accompanying text serves as an example for the moderation to be carried out by game masters. Depending on the audience and types of services provided by the respective libraries, the fields can be renamed or more spaces can be added.

NEUTRAL SPACES

Researcher's Start Field

Points:

Each player starts with 5 Coins but 0 Reputations Points.

1st round:

Your scientific project was accepted! It is mandatory to share your findings and gained knowledge. During the game, you will experience different events that can happen in academic publishing and what you need to keep in mind.

When crossing over in further rounds:

+2 Coins

Action Field

Players pull an Action Card and follow the instructions on the respective cards..

COUNSELING AND SUPPORT SERVICES

Team Bibliometrics and Reporting

Points:

+1 Reputation Point

Storytelling:

Your library's Bibliometrics and Reporting Team provides advice on enhancing the visibility of your research achievements. They may help analyze and monitor your scientific output and offer support when setting up a research profile.

Office Office for Good Scientific Practice and Ethical Principles

Points:

+1 Reputation Point

Storytelling:

You seek advice at the Office for Good Scientific Practice and Ethical Principles to avoid plagiarism in your publication. In addition, the office provides guidance for all other ethical questions during your research and publication processes.

Research Data Management

Points:

+1 Reputation Point

Storytelling:

You sought advice from the advice from your library and published your research data accompanying your paper. This enhances the visibility of your research. The team supports you in all phases, from data collection to preservation and data publication, as well as offers tools to build a data management plan (DMP).

University Publishing

Points:

+1 Reputation Point and -1 Coin

Storytelling:

You publish open access through the university publisher.

Publication Fund

Points:

+1 Coin

Storytelling:

Your paper was published in a gold open access journal. This involves publication costs, so-called Article Processing Charges (APC), but your library covers the Article Processing Charges (APC) for you.

Repository

Points:

+1 Reputation Point

Storytelling:

You publish your paper as green open access in a scientific repository. A repository provides a publication platform for all researchers and scientific staff.

OPEN ACCESS TYPES

Green OA

Points:

+1 Reputation Point

Storytelling:

You publish your paper, which was inaccessible at first, as a secondary publication in green open access model.

Gold OA

Points:

+1 Reputation Point and -1 Coin

Storytelling:

You published your paper in a gold open access journal. This way it is accessible worldwide, and your findings are reusable for everyone.

Diamond OA

Points:

+1 Reputation Point

Storytelling:

You published your findings in a diamond open access journal. This way you do not incur any costs, and the article is accessible for everyone nevertheless.

Closed Access

Points:

- 3 Reputation Points

Storytelling:

You published in a closed-access journal. Therefore, the publisher owns the rights to your article, including all visualizations, and your findings remain behind a paywall. This way your research is less visible and accessible to other scientists.

CHALLENGES

Copyright Trap

Points:

Skip one round or pay 3 Coins

Storytelling:

You want to use one of your old images in a new publication. But since you did not pay attention when signing the contract, the publisher owns all the rights on your previously published pictures, and you are not allowed to use them directly. Instead, you must buy back the rights to reuse your illustration from the publisher.

GAME MANAGEMENT

Group size

We recommend 2–5 players at once. This way the game can be supervised by 1 to 2 game masters. In addition, the time between turns is reduced.

Time management

Each game is expected to run for ca. 15 minutes. The estimated play time does not include the time required for setup. For the game setup, one should add an extra 10 minutes.

Notes on group supervision

Ideally, the group size should not be larger than 5 to 6 persons. Nevertheless, it is possible to manage bigger groups. One possibility is to divide the players into 3 to 4 teams. Especially for families with children, this solution is very suitable.

We do not recommend playing with several groups independently at the same time. The field test showed this only leads to confusion and frustration.

To handle larger groups, it is also reasonable to expand the timeframe and appoint more game masters as support. One possible solution is to assign certain roles like main game master and assistant game master, who handle action cards and tokens.

FEEDBACK

Help us improve!

The present version is the status quo after one year of game development and represents a successful interim result for us. Nevertheless, we want to constantly improve the game concept and material. Please, feel free to give us any feedback, remarks, and criticism, especially when testing the game. We greatly appreciate your input!

[Feedback Link](#)

Copyright Information

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